

Investigating Writing Anxiety among ESL Undergraduate Learners at a Private Sector University, Sindh Pakistan

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Abstract: The study aims to investigate the main sources of anxiety when ESL students write. For the purpose of this study, a quantitative method research strategy has been chosen, and the data was gathered through the administration of questionnaires among participants belonging to five different departments. The questionnaire, named ESL Writing Anxiety Questionnaire, acquires responses from the participants that are students. In order to carry out the data analysis technique for the quantitative surveys, descriptive statistics were used through SPSS 22. The findings revealed that the factors found to be playing a role in giving students English writing anxiety include the students having no grip over strategies and techniques of English composition, lack of feedback, fear of negative feedback, lecture methods, and general confusion. To conclude, data derived from the questionnaire reveal that even though learners are truly anxious regarding writing skills, their learning environment, past experiences, and teacher's support plays a vital role in contributing to their stress and negative attitudes when learning English language.

Keywords: Anxiety, Quantitative, ELT, ESL

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1: Introduction

Writing has a complex nature and due to this, many EFL learners consider it a difficult task because they do not have sound vocabulary. Also, they lack in grammatical information and have no sufficient or adequate language skills. All these lacking ultimately develop problems to perform and write effectively in an ESL classroom. One of the authors in his study explains one of the demanding tasks of English language is writing, especially for the ones who possess a background of English as a foreign language. Since it is a demanding task, there are other different problems which occur consequently and the problem of writing anxiety is one of them. (Zailaini et al, 2015).

In Pakistan, English language is only taught in a formal setting of an ESL classroom. In these classes, teachers do not have sufficient knowledge of English language as well as there are very limited numbers of resources to teach a foreign language. As a result, to learn the language formally is limited. Consequently, learners are merely trained to use the basic stages and levels of the target language; English. Moreover, according to Rababah (2002), in the acquisition of a

foreign language, the hardest domain to master is writing and majority of the learners make errors in it. For example, according to another study, in Pakistan, undergraduate and even postgraduate learners who use English as their target language are weak at writing skills. (Mashoori& Iqbal, 2007).

Furthermore, in another study, Zhang (2011) explored the clear connection amid students' performance in writing tasks and ESL writing anxiety. As per the results of her study, those students who received lower grades had writing anxiety at a higher level. In addition to it, in few of other research, there is no positive correlation is observed among the anxiety which is caused by writing task as well as the achievement of those students, (Hassan, 2001, Cheng, 2004, Daud et al., 2007 and Zhang, 2011). Moreover, studies in Pakistan have mostly focused on the reading and speaking related problems and anxieties. Therefore, this study focuses on ESL students' causes of writing anxiety.

2: Literature Review

In the ESL writing literature, there are several studies that show how ESL writing produces anxiety for the learners which affect their performance. For example, Cheng (1998) has stated that the majority of people will experience anxiety at some point in their lives. However, some circumstances, including interpersonal interactions, cause anxiety more than others. Numerous syndromes have been identified, defined, validated, and promoted as unique predispositions likely to impair one's day-to-day functioning as a result of the extensive research on interpersonal communication anxiety. Because the study of writing apprehension started as a subset of research on communication apprehension, the efforts of this research trend can also be credited with bringing awareness to the presence and importance of writing anxiety (Smith, 1984).

Over the past few decades, a significant corpus of research has focused on writing anxiety as a particular element of second language acquisition. According to Bloom (1981), writing anxiety appears to be largely situation-specific, self-limiting, generally observable, and most crucially, appears to be largely amenable to logical instruction. Writing anxiety has been shown to have a crippling effect on pupils' performance in language studies. The effects of writing anxiety on writing processes and behaviours were outlined by Cheng (2004). These effects included physiological effects, which manifest as uncomfortable tension or uneasiness, cognitive interference with the writing process, and avoidance of writing. In order to examine the associations between the specific writing anxiety and writing performance, he also used the participants' performance on a timed English essay writing task as an indication of their English writing performance. The results revealed a substantial inverse relationship between performance and anxiety.

A general dislike of writing and situations that people believe would necessitate some writing, along with the possibility of having that writing evaluated, is known as Second Language Writing Anxiety (SLWA) (Hassan, 2001). Due to its profound influence on language learning, second language acquisition researchers and teachers have discovered it to be worthwhile of study. In foreign language classes, it is common for students to experience unfavourable emotions like anxiety, dread, and low motivation. The severity of these emotions may cause students to skip language sessions or even steer clear of language-learning circumstances (Genc&Yayli, 2019). Studies have also revealed that students who use productive skills, such as writing and speaking, report feeling a lot of anxiety when learning (Hilleson, 1996; Zhang, 2001).

Research was conducted by Cheng (2004) by creating an initial pool of scale items from 65 reports of L2 writing anxiety from EFL students. In order to create a draught version of the L2 writing anxiety scale for future development and evaluation in the official study, a pilot test on the original pool of items was done. The formal study included a sample of 421 EFL majors enrolled in seven different Taiwanese colleges. The Second Language Writing Anxiety Inventory (SLWAI), which consists of three subscales: Somatic Anxiety, Cognitive Anxiety, and Avoidance Behaviour, was constructed using exploratory factor analysis. The reliability of the SLWAI total scale and subscales was evaluated using correlation and factor analysis in addition to reliability coefficients. The findings imply that the SLWAI's overall scale and each of its distinct subscales have good reliability and sufficient validity.

Another study by Daud, Daud and Kassim (2007) was conducted at MARA University of Technology. 186 third-year university students who had taken Diploma in Accountancy and Diploma in Business courses served as the study's subjects. The students' skill levels varied because those who simply received a pass on the English exam were also admitted to the programme with the better students due to their strong performance in other pertinent courses. Writing anxiety and writing performance are investigated in this study using a correlational research approach, and predictions about the nature of the link between the two are made using the findings of the observed association. The questionnaire for this study's participants was finished after which an internal consistency check was performed on the Daly-Miller Writing Apprehension Test results using SPSS version 10.1. The findings revealed a strong and favourable relationship between the language-related aspects and writing apprehension level (namely, vocabulary and language use). This shows that there is a clear connection between the degree of writing anxiety and essay writing proficiency. In this instance, performance in language-related dimensions increased when anxiety levels were lower (as shown by a high logit score) and decreased when anxiety levels were greater.

Furthermore, study conducted by Cheng (1998) explored the conceptual connections between writing and speaking proficiency in a second language, as well as their relationships with one another, was done. The researchers opted for an adapted version of Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope's (1986) Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale in order to operationalise second language class anxiety (FLCAS). The researcher also used an adapted second-language Writing Apprehension Test developed by Daly and Miller (1975) was used to measure second-language writing anxiety (SLWAT). This survey was conducted in the spring of (1997) with a total of 433 English majors enrolled in English speaking and writing courses at four Taiwanese institutions. The participants answered questions from a survey that included the FLCAS, SLWAT, and a background questionnaire in Chinese. At the end of the semester, the participants' final scores in their English speaking and writing classes were compiled and utilised as indicators of second language proficiency. In the research, the two anxiety measures' principal components and correlational analyses revealed that the two conceptions of second language class anxiety and second language writing anxiety are linked but separate. For the FLCAS, two components were taken out: Low English-Speaking Self-Confidence and General Performance Anxiety in the English Classroom. Low Self-Confidence in English Writing, Aversiveness of Writing in English, and English Writing Evaluation Apprehension were chosen as the three components for the SLWAT. The two anxiety measures' principal components and correlational analyses revealed that the two conceptions of second language class anxiety and second language writing anxiety are linked but separate. For the FLCAS, two components were taken out: Low English-Speaking Self-Confidence and General Performance Anxiety in the English Classroom. Low Self-Confidence in English Writing, Aversiveness of Writing in English, and English Writing Evaluation Apprehension were chosen as the three components for the SLWAT.

3: Research Methodology

The objective of the present study is to analyze the factors that contribute to writing anxiety. For the purpose of this study, a quantitative method has been chosen, and the data was gathered through the administration of a questionnaire among ESL learners belonging to five different departments.

Quantitative research design has been opt by the researcher for this study. Creswell (1994) has provided a very succinct definition of quantitative research as a type of research that is "explaining phenomena by collecting numerical data that are analysed using mathematically based methods (in particular statistics)".

For the questionnaire of this research, participants were chosen from a total of five different departments at a university located in Sindh, Pakistan, which is part of the private sector. The researcher chose 20 students; both male and female from each of the departments to participate in the study. As a whole, there were a total of one hundred ($n=100$)

undergraduate students participating in this project. The table below presents the data of the ESL learners who participated in the present study.

Table 1: Departments and frequency of students

Department the Students Belong to	
Valid	Frequency
Islamic learning	20
D Pharmacy	20
Education	20
Mass communication	20
Business administration	20
Total	100

The present study used a random sampling in order to recruit the participants who took part in the study. Within random sampling approach, each person in the population has an equal chance of being chosen for the sample that will be taken from the larger population. The data is selected at random using a random number table or a list of random numbers generated by a computer. It's also possible to do it with a lottery, utilising money notes, and other methods (Acharya et al., 2013).

The questionnaire, named ESL Writing Anxiety Questionnaire, acquires responses from the participants that were students. This questionnaire was created by Zhang Hongxia. The questionnaire consisted of 15 questions, all of them targeted towards the students' perception of the level of writing anxiety they think they have. The questionnaire was built on 5-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly agree, agree, neither agree/ nor disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree.

In order to carry out the data analysis technique for the quantitative surveys, descriptive statistics was used through SPSS 22. In the software, data was put regarding each of the questions' answers. Mean and standard deviation were calculated by SPSS, helping the researcher draw a conclusion through evidence and the readers to better understand the causes of writing anxiety.

4: Result and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the elements that contribute to writing anxiety. For the purpose of this study, a quantitative method has been chosen, and the data is gathered through the administration of the questionnaire to participants. The first questionnaire, i.e., ESL Writing Anxiety Questionnaire, gathered responses from the participants that are students belonging to five different departments.

4.1: Students' Perceptions regarding their Writing Skills

The researcher in the present study presents the analysis of the data gathered through questionnaire using descriptive statistics. The data was run on SPSS version 22. The questions were asked from the participants through the Likert scale. There were individual questions that they had to agree or disagree with, rather than Likert-type questions that when

combined would describe a personality trait or attitude, which is why the main focus by the researcher was towards mean, median, and standard deviation, most suitable for the questionnaire's type.

Table 2: Factors Affecting Students' Writing Skills

S. no.	Questions	N	Mean	Median	SD
1	No clue what to write, especially when time bound	100	2.05	2.00	.857
2	Difficulty in writing English composition	100	2.58	2.00	1.13
3	Fear of negative marking from teacher	100	3.4	4.00	1.271
4	It makes me sad my English writing skills are weak	100	3.41	4.00	1.190
5	I have no writing practice inside and outside my class	100	3.51	4.00	1.159
6	I have no grip over strategies and techniques of English composition	100	3.83	4.00	.975
7	The feedback from my teacher on English write-ups are effective	100	3.45	3.00	.999
8	I feel anxious to write as my teacher does not provide enough resources for writing	100	2.63	2.50	1.051

9	For writing tasks, my teacher uses lecture method, making me anxious	100	3.29	3.00	1.131
10	I feel confused when writing task is assigned due to lack of guidance from teacher	100	3.52	4.00	1.010
11	I consider my writing skills to be very poor	100	3.21	3.00	.967
12	I consider my writing skills are poor	100	2.76	3.00	1.111
13	I consider my writing skills are fair	100	2.74	3.00	1.169
14	I consider my writing skills are good	100	3.97	4.00	.926
15	I consider my writing skills are excellent	100	3.55	4.00	.957

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics of the data obtained through the first questionnaire, which was directed towards the students from different departments. The first column labelled as 'N' shows the number of total participants. The mean value in the next column presents the majority of responses that has been from the participants. In the questionnaire, Likert Scale was used, in which, 1 represented 'strongly agree' while 5 referred to 'strongly disagree'. In order to calculate the median, it is assumed that the five discrete categories on the five-point scale are actually five continuous random variables. As an example, it is believed that everyone who chose 4 (i.e., disagree) is equally divided between 3.5 and 4.49. Similar to this, it is presumed that everyone who chose a 5 (strongly disagree) would fall between 4.5 and 5.49. After these responses have been converted, the median is determined.

After that, the next column is for median which shows the midpoint value. Then, the researcher calculated the standard deviation which shows how respondents differ in their attitudes with regard to certain issues. Higher the standard deviation is, means the answers of the respondents are diverse, whereas lower the standard deviation is, means more similar the answers of the respondents are.

In Table 2, the first question has a mean score of 2.05, which means majority of the participants agree that they do not have an idea what to write especially when there is a time limit the statement and the response is also homogenous as the standard deviation is lower than 1. In the next question, the response of the participants is between agree and

neutral, therefore the standard deviation is also high, lying at 1.13, proving that the students find it difficult to write English Composition, is quite diverse. The next questions regarding fear of negative marking, making students sad that their English writing skills are weak, and the statement that they have no writing practice inside and outside their class, respectively, all have a response indicating that the participants were either in a neutral stance or in disagreement of these statements, which is why the standard deviation is high for these statements as the response is diverse.

The sixth statement regarding having no grip over strategies and techniques of English composition are mostly responded with agreement from most of the participants. Then, the next statement is if the students get feedback from their teachers on their English write-ups, and the response is mostly same and towards disagreement, meaning their teachers do not provide feedback to their write-ups. The next question regarding feeling anxiety to write as teacher does not provide enough resources for writing has a response rate mostly directing towards agreement. However, it can be assumed that some neutral responses are present as the standard deviation is at 1.051; therefore, it makes the responses diverse.

The next question is regarding the teacher using traditional lecture methods to teach writing tasks in class which has a median of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.131. Even though there are a lot of agreements in this question, a lot of responses are towards neutrality as well. Next question is regarding feeling confused about writing tasks assigned to students due to lack of guidance from the teacher are lying in neutrality or agreement; however, we can assume that most of the answers are toward agreement as the standard deviation is not too high (0.010) meaning the responses are similar to one another.

The next question prove to us that most students consider their English writing skills to be very poor and the standard deviation (1.111) shows that the response rate is similar. The last two questions ask the participants if they consider their writing skills to be good or excellent, upon which there are neutral to disagreement responses with a low standard deviation (.926 and .957, respectively), meaning the responses are similar.

To conclude the analysis of Table 2, we can state that most of the anxiety of the participants is driven from being time bound, having low grip over strategies and techniques of English composition, lack of feedback from teachers, lack of resources for writing provided by the teacher, and feeling confused due to lack of guidance from the teacher. Majority of the students are very sure that they are poor at their English writing skills.

5: Summary of Main Findings

According to the data obtained from students through a questionnaire, the researcher was able to draw out that majority of the students were aware of the fact that they do have writing anxiety which could be linked to their lack of knowledge or weak English writing skills. Another significant factor observed by the researcher was that most of the students were of the opinion that the lack of guidance and resources provided by the teacher also contribute to their writing anxiety. Another factor is that teachers should constantly remind their students that they will not be harshly dealt with if they have troubles understanding English composition or writing skills. They should affirm them in class that their writing task is going to be between them and the teacher, and that no other student is going to get a hold of it or make fun of them for what they wrote. This way, students will understand and work with a relaxed mind, and they will be able to perform better when they do not have a fear of negative or harsh response from their teacher or fellow classmates.

6: Conclusion

The main aim of the present research was to investigate writing anxiety in ESL undergraduate students of a public university. Therefore, the objectives of this research were to investigate the factors which cause anxiety among ESL learners in writing skills at a public university.

The most common factors found to be playing the biggest role in giving students English writing anxiety include the students having little or no grip over strategies and techniques of English composition, lack of feedback provided by the teachers, lecture methods or traditional methods being used by the teacher for teaching writing skills, and feeling confused due to lack of guidance from the teacher. Majority of the students perceive themselves to have poor English writing skills. This perception comes into alignment with the teachers' response also indicating that they know their students have writing anxiety. Teachers need not to negatively criticize the students leading to their self esteem being shattered. Even if the present teacher is nice and gives constructive criticism, it may be possible that the previous teachers the students had were not that kind, therefore they need to be constantly reassured that their writing task will be dealt with in a constructive manner. Students also prefer a welcoming and friendly environment when they are studying, not just a language but any subject. Teachers need to assure that their class environment may be set in a way that is open and friendly so that the students are relaxed and can perform to the best of their abilities.

Conclusively, one can easily observe from the data derived from the questionnaire that even though learners are truly anxious regarding writing skills, their learning environment, past experiences, and teacher's support plays a vital role in contributing to their stress and negative attitudes when learning English language.

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